

**DIVERSITY AND DISTRIBUTION OF VASCULAR PLANTS IN BATAGARAWA
LOCAL GOVERNMENT AREA AND THEIR MEDICINAL IMPORTANCE**

BY

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**UNDER THE SUPERVISION OF
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**BEING A PROJECT SUBMITTED TO THE
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(B.SC) DEGREE IN BIOLOGY**

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DECLARATION

I declare that this project research titled “Diversity and Distribution of Vascular Plants in Batagarawa Local Government Area and Their Medicinal Importance” was written and carried out by me under the supervision of Mal. Abdullahi Shehu Ado and has not been submitted in any way or form to any academic institution for the award of any degree. Information(s) obtained from both published and unpublished sources had been acknowledged and referenced.

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CERTIFICATION

This is to certify that this project research titled “Diversity and Distribution of Vascular Plants in Batagarawa Local Government Area and Their Medicinal Importance” was written by Aisha Aminu Zakari with Registration Number NAS/BIO/19/3072 was carried out under my supervision.

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APPROVAL PAGE

This project research titled “Diversity and Distribution of Vascular Plants in Batagarawa Local Government Area and Their Medicinal Importance” by Aisha Aminu Zakari with registration number NAS/BIO/19/3072 meets the requirements governing the award of Bachelor of Science Degree in Biology of Al-Qalam University Katsina. The project research has been examined and approved in partial fulfilment of the requirement for the award of B. Sc in Biology.

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DEDICATION

This project research is dedicated to my parents for always believing in me, loving, supporting and guiding me.

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ABSTRACT

This research work was conducted within Batagarawa LGA. The present study was aimed to document the diversity and distribution of vascular plants in Batagarawa Local Government Area, Katsina state – Nigeria. Administration of structured questionnaires and interviews were employed. A total number of 93 respondents were interviewed. Five sites were randomly selected and five quadrants were also established in each site. Plant species in each of the sites were identified and ethnobotanical information for the identified plants was obtained through interview administration of a semi-structured questionnaire. A total of sixty-five plant species belonging to 32 families were recorded from the study area, with Fabaceae, Moraceae, and Combretaceae having the highest frequency. Shannon-Wiener diversity index was used to assess species richness and evenness. The highest species richness and maximum diversity were observed in site E, while site D was with the least species richness and diversity. The evenness was more or less similar for each community except that the maximum evenness was observed in site B and in site D. Leaves were also found to be the most harvested plant parts for the preparation of the remedies followed by stem/bark and roots. In the preparation of medicines, single plants were used to prepare the medicines to cure the diseases rather than mixing with each other. The routes of administration are mainly internal in which oral administration is the common one. *Azadirachta indica*, *Anarcadium occidentale*, *Mangifera indica*, *Diospyrus mespiliformis*, *Ceiba pentandra* and *Moringa oleifera* are among the most common and abundant medicinal plants in the study area. The results of the Ethnobotanical study revealed that most of the vascular plants in Batagarawa LGA are being utilized in traditional medicine practice.

Include keywords

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Documenting the distribution of biodiversity and understanding their patterns is the foremost fundamental step in developing effective conservation strategies and planning sustainable utilization of these resources for the future (Linder and Verboom, 2015). The study of floristic composition is one of the best ways to understand the patterns of biodiversity by classifying groups of organisms into meaningful geographical units at different scales (Li *et al.*, 2015). Based on the similarity of floristic assemblages and the degree of endemism, systems of floristic regions have provided spatially explicit frameworks for many large-scale ecological, evolutionary, and conservation studies (Sosefet *et al.*, 2017), such as those of the whole world (Kreft and Jetz, 2010), China (Li *et al.*, 2015; Zhang *et al.*, 2016), and tropical Africa (Gehrke and Linder, 2014; Linder, 2014). However, due to the continuous updating of plant science, such as plant classification systems, species distribution data, and floristic division methods, the division of the flora in many areas needs further improvement (Sosef *et al.*, 2017).

The identification of the centre's endemic species is vital for the recognition of biodiversity hotspots (Possingham and Wilson, 2005), and it is also an essential part of planning regional conservation management (Norooziet *et al.*, 2018). As endemism generally results from a complex association of evolutionary, ecological, and social processes at various spatial and temporal scales (Bose *et al.*, 2016; Gaucherelet *et al.*, 2016), the centre's endemism is usually incongruent with the species richness (Orme *et al.*, 2005). Thus, we need to analyze different perspectives and weigh various measuring indices to identify endemic species centres, for example, endemic

species richness and weighted endemism have been commonly applied to the measurement of species endemism and in the detection of their centres (Linder, 2001; Sosa *et al.*, 2018).

Since ancient times, plants have been indispensable sources of both preventive and curative traditional medicine preparations for human beings and livestock (Salisuet *et al.*, 2015). Many of today's drugs are derived from plants sources although research in plants continued and plants were still used as the basis for some drugs development, the dominant interest is shifted to the laboratory (Lowe *et al.*, 2000). According to World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 80% of the world's population relies on traditional medicine to fulfil their daily health needs due to poverty and lack of access to modern medicine (WHO, 2002). An estimate of about 3000 plant species are used by approximately 200,000 traditional healers in this country. More than 60% of South Africans consult these traditional healers for their health care needs and cultural practices on a regular basis (Abubakar *et al.*, 2017).

The medicinal value of plants lies in some chemical substances that produce a definite physiological action on the human body. Medicinal plants are plants that have one or more of their parts containing important phytochemicals that can be used for therapeutic purposes or as additives in pharmaceutical products (Bentley and Trimen, 2007). These phytochemicals appear to be of great benefit to humans and their consumption has fewer side effects as compared to pharmaceutical synthetic drugs (Barisi and Omodele, 2014). Traditional medicine, with medicinal plants as their most important component, is sold in marketplaces or prescribed by traditional healers in their homes (Von Maydell, 1996). Medicinal plants have important contributions to the healthcare system of local communities as the main source of medicine for the majority of the rural population. Plants have not only nutritional values but also, in the eyes

of the local people, they have medicinal and ritual or magical values. The ethnomedicinal healing systems vary across cultures (John, 1893).

Medicinal plants constitute an effective source of both traditional and modern medicine. These plants have been shown to have genuine utility and about 80% of the rural population depends on them as primary healthcare (Akinyemi, 2000). Plants have been used as a source of remedies for the treatment of many diseases since ancient times and people of all continents especially Africa have this old tradition. Despite the remarkable progress in synthetic organic medicinal products of the twentieth century, over 25% of prescribed medicines in industrialized countries are derived directly or indirectly from plants (Newman *et al.*, 2000).

The ethnobotanical survey is an important step in the identification, selection and development of the therapeutic agents from medicinal plants. In Ethnobotany and natural products chemistry, the mode of preparation and administration of herbal preparations are often crucial variables in determining efficacy in pharmacological evaluation (Abubakar *et al.*, 2016). The Use of phytomedicines for the treatment of diseases is a known practice in many rural communities in Africa. However, these plants are taken by the people without any consideration of the possible toxic effect of components in such plants. The surveys have shown that these traditional medicines have been found to be effective (Sani and Aliyu, 2011).

Ethnobotany and ethnomedical studies are today recognized as the most effective method of identifying new medicinal plants or refocusing on those plants reported in earlier studies for the possible extraction of beneficial bioactive compounds (Thirumalai *et al.*, 2009). The need for continued ethnobotanical research to find and document important medicinal plants cannot be over-emphasised (Wintola and Afolayan, 2010).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

Despite the increasing acceptance of traditional medicine indigenous knowledge on traditional remedies is not adequately documented. The available knowledge on the use of plant preparations in traditional medicine is important but the dissemination of this valuable knowledge is progressively diminishing. In addition, the conservation of ethnobotanical knowledge as part of living cultural knowledge and practice between communities and the environment is essential for biodiversity conservation (Martin, 1995). Therefore, documentation of plants used in traditional medicine is urgent so that the knowledge can be preserved and plants conserved, and sustainably managed and utilized by the majority of the local people.

There is, however, a need to collect more data from the knowledge holders of their use of diverse plants in the management of different kinds of diseases. These undisclosed ethnobotanical data are important to be collected and urgently documented as the traditional knowledge about plants and their medicinal use is fast disappearing due to socioeconomic change, land use, climate change, and plant overexploitation.

1.3 Justification of the Research

For centuries, people have been using herbal medicines for the treatment of some diseases. Plant species may have different uses in different countries as well as different areas of the same country. In spite of such a rich cultural heritage and relatively rich flora, the number of scientific ethnobotanical field surveys, at least published in the international journals, among the regional communities is very low. However, the best of my knowledge, diversity and traditional uses of medicinal vascular plants in Batagarawa have not been studied.

Also, it has now become more important than ever to record and preserve the traditional knowledge on medicinal plants, in order to aid the discovery of new drugs and possibly to find improved applications of traditional medicine. In addition, documenting the results of scientific

research into traditional medicine may also help conserve an important part of an indigenous people's cultural heritage for future generations.

The documentation of indigenous knowledge through ethnobotanical studies is important in the conservation and utilization of biological resources. The identification of local names, scientific names and indigenous uses of plants not only preserves indigenous knowledge but also facilitates future research on the safety and efficacy of medicinal plants in treatment of various ailments. This will ensure that traditional knowledge about the use of these plants is conserved. It will also facilitate the discovery of new sources of drugs and promote sustainable use of medicinal plant resources in Katsina. In addition conservation of medicinal plants will add value to the recreational environment as well as health improvement through sustained ecosystems.

1.4 Aim

This study was aimed to investigate the diversity and distribution of vascular plants in Batagarawa Local Government Area and their medicinal importance.

1.5 Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study were:

1. To identify the vascular plants in Batagarawa LGA
2. To determine the composition and diversity of vascular plants in Batagarawa LGA
3. To assess the ethnobotanical importance of vascular plants in Batagarawa LGA

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 An Overview on Vascular Plants

Vascular plants are also called tracheophytes. The term “Tracheophyta” is derived from the Greek word trachea (meaning a duct—a vessel in plants). The vascular plants are highly ordered, and land plants, including flowering vascular plants and ferns (Sani *et al.*, 2012). The vascular plants are well-developed and advanced plants that include ferns, seed plants, angiosperms, and gymnosperms. The vascular plants have vascular tissues, including xylem and phloem for conducting water and integrating food, respectively (Doun *et al.*, 2019).

Vascular plants contain two main aspects; the presence of xylem and phloem, and all the vascular plants are seed plants. The vascular plant contains xylem and phloem known as vascular tissues, for instance, conifers, flowering plants, and ferns (Sani *et al.*, 2012). The vascular plants include all the seed-containing plants, angiosperms (flowering plants), gymnosperms, and the pteridophytes (lycophytes, horsetails, and ferns). Many vascular plants are land plants. The vascular plants include a wide range of plants from all the angiosperms, gymnosperms, and other pteridophytes (Evlowet *al.*, 2016). These groups are scientifically named Tracheophyta, Equisetopsida, and Tracheobionta. The term eutracheophyte is used for all other types of vascular plants. Vascular plants are advanced plants with a transporting function that occurred through the xylem and phloem. The glucose (produced during photosynthesis), gases, water, minerals, and nutrients are circulated throughout the plant (Deelewelet *al.*, 2005). Vascular plants are eukaryotes. They are distinguished from prokaryotes by having cells with a nucleus and other membrane-bound cellular structures. Vascular plants are also known as tube plants (tracheophytes). The presence of vascular tissues such as xylem (tube-like) and phloem (tubular

cells) plays a role in distributing food and water to the plant cells. Other ordinary characteristics include stems, leaves, and roots that hold the plant and provide support (Owler *et al.*, 2016).

Despite common characteristics such as leaves and stems, both plants are highly differentiated based on the complex vascular system and other side characteristics. However, an easy way to understand vascular and non-vascular plants' differences is to distinguish based on characteristics (Garba *et al.*, 2016).

2.1.1 Structure of a Vascular Plant

The vascular plant's internal structure is well organized, and the arrangement of cells is differentiated compared to non-vascular plants with congested structures. Different species of vascular plants have unique, differentiated patterns of vascular tissues (Feyme *et al.*, 2017).

Moreover, the xylem transports the water, absorbed from the roots to the whole plant body, and is made up of lignin (structural protein) and dead cells. The absorption of water into tissues occurs through the pressure exerted on water from different directions. Further, the water flows upward through the xylem. The leaves then used the water for transpirational purposes. The small opening in the leaves called stomata evaporates the water out of the plant. This transpirational process further pulls the water in the xylem (Umuni *et al.*, 2009).

Furthermore, the phloem, responsible for extracting the energy from the sunlight and converting it into chemical energy to form glucose, is made up of living cells (partially). These cells help in the transportation of glucose through transport proteins present in the cell membranes. Both structures, xylem, and phloem are interlinked, helping dilute the glucose and transporting it throughout the plant body (Ahmed, 1998).

2.1.2 Economic Importance of Vascular Plants

Vascular plants have been found to provide a bundle of benefits to humans for economic grounds. The leaves or fronds of ferns are attractive and beautiful, making the plant a more favourite ornamental plant. These plants can grow and develop in low light and are used for decorating homes. Some ferns such as Fiddlehead, Polypodium, and Licorice fern are used as food and side dishes, popular among native Americans, France tribes, and Pacific Northwest coastal tribes (Hagnoon *et al* 1997). The rhizomes of ferns are sweet. Moreover, native Americans use the fern for curing sore throat. Another economic benefit of a vascular plant that impacted human life is coal deposits throughout the world due to the plants' burring in the Carboniferous period. Thus, providing humans with an ultimate source of energy (keep in mind that excessive use of coal is one reason for global warming). The angiosperms are abundant and produce flowers that enhance the environment due to their beauty (Hagnoon *et al.*, 1997). They are a good source of medicine, food, clothing fibre, and wood. These angiosperms are economically beneficial for humans, such as cotton crops, fruits crops (mango, orange, etc.) that boost the country's economy. The agricultural countries are based on crops, such as wheat, rice, maize, cereals, and vice-versa that keep the country in progress and trade all these crops, the country, and foreign currency, leading to the increase in economic levels (Klown *et al.*, 2017). Many angiosperms are sources of drugs used to cure different diseases by producing chemicals that are significant for medicinal purposes. Some species of gymnosperms are edible and thus a source of food. Other gymnosperms are used for making medicine, as ornaments, and other industrial products such as gum, tannins, and vice versa (Rashow *et al.*, 2015).

2.2 Ethnobotany

Ethnobotany simply means investigating plants used by primitive societies in various parts of the world (Bodeker, 1994). Though the term “**Ethnobotany**” was not coined until 1895 by the U.S Botanist John William Harshberger, the history of the field began long before that time. It is the study of how people of a particular culture and region make use of indigenous plants. Ethnobotanists explore how plants are used for such things as food, shelter, medicines, clothing, hunting and religious ceremonies. Ethnobotany has its roots in botany as the study of plants. Many of today’s drugs have been derived from plant sources, although research in plants have continued, plants were still used as the basis for some drug development (Sheldon *et al.*, 1997).

2.2.1 Traditional Uses of Plants in Nigeria

Plants have been used from ancient times to attempt cures for diseases and to secure relief from physical suffering (Akerete, 1998). Ancient people all had acquired some knowledge of medicinal plants, oftentimes, these primitive attempts at medicine were based on superstition and speculation. Evil spirits in the body were thought to be the cause of medicinal problems. They could be driven out of the body through the use of poisonous or disagreeable habitats. Medicine men or women of a tribe were usually charged with knowledge of such plants. The progress of medicine has often been guided by such earlier observations and beliefs. Traditional medical practice is an important part of the primary health care delivery system in most of the developing world (Akerete, 1998). According to the World Health Organization, an estimated 3.5 billion people in the developing world depends on medicinal plants as part of their primary health care (Balick and Cox, 1996).

2.2.2 Plants as Source of Medicine

Plants used for the treatment of disorders are known as medicinal plants. The medicinal plants are used by people for medicinal purposes and to build or maintain good health, stave off disease or promote recovery from illness or misfortune. Plants are used as a source of medicine due to the presence of certain chemicals/active ingredients inside their body. It is found that plants are playing a lead role in therapy (Srivastava, 2000). Even today, traditional medicines (largely herbs) are supporting the primary health care for the majority of people globally use herbs more than the conventional or allopathic medicines (Farnsworth *et al.*, 1985). The plants have been used as medicines since the beginning of human civilization (Hill, 1952) and have been a source of treatment of the common day ailments. The utilization of the plants for such purpose is referred to as ethnomedicine and the branch of botany associated with this is ethnobotany (Srivastava, 2000).

Adelanwa and Tijjani, (2013) conducted an ethnomedical survey of the flora in the Kumbotso Local Government Area of Kano state the authors used oral interviews as their major methodology for data collection purposes from traditional medicine practitioners, herbalists, village heads, herb Sellers and elders. Results obtained reveal that there are wide acceptability and use of plants for ethnomedicine by a large number of the people in Kumbotso Local Government Area Kano state. Further, fifty-five (55) plant species belonging to thirty-three (33) families were identified as a cure for twelve (12) different kinds of ailments. However, the authors claimed that over time, the use of medicinal plants for curing ailments might go extinct given the fact that there seems to be a lack of interest by the younger generation in this direction although this claim was never investigated by the authors.

Yar'adua and Adb El-Ghani, (2015) embarked on the ethnobotanical survey of edible plants sold in three (3) markets found within the Katsina metropolis. Questionnaires, semi-structured

interviews, e.t.c. were employed as tools for data collection. The authors gathered fifty-four (54) plant species all of which belonged, The varied number of species were obtained in each market with Kofar Marusa market recording the highest while the central market had the least. Further analysis of the result revealed that most used plants belong to the Fabaceae family with five (5) species. In a bid to improve upon this study, the authors conducted by recommending that a sufficient study be conducted in this direction, this might partly be as a result of the study areas considered which are very limited when looking at the Katsina Metropolis as a whole.

2.2.2 Medicinal plants in The traditional healthcare system

A medicinal plant is one used by people for medicinal purposes—to build or maintain health, stave off disease, or promote recovery from illness or misfortune. No precise definition is possible, given this wide scope and because the use of plants as medicines grades into their use for other purposes, for example, for food, personal hygiene, beauty-care, psychological support and spiritual practices (Hamilton, 2008).

Medicinal plants continue to provide health security to rural people in primary healthcare. Healthcare and botany have evolved as inseparable domains of human activity: the medicine man (shaman) is often regarded as the first botanical professional in human history. Whereas western medicine, as taught in most medical schools around the world, has largely switched from natural to manufactured drugs, plant products are still of paramount importance in the traditional healthcare systems of developing countries (Cunningham *et al.*, 2008).

Medicinal plants are the roots of medical practice. The Medicinal plant uses range from antimicrobial ‘chewing sticks’ for dental care and the treatment of internal parasites to symbolic uses. In fact, of the global total of about 300,000 flowering plant species, more than 50,000 are

used for medicinal purposes, with an estimated 2500 species of medicinal and aromatic plants traded worldwide, most still collected from wild sources (Schippmann *et al.*, 2006).

2.3.3 Medicinal plants and health-seeking Behaviour

Reasons for the use of herbal medicine/medicinal plants include the perceived efficacy of traditional systems, the high cost of allopathic medical care and cultural beliefs, as well as the lack of available medical doctors. The holistic, philosophical character of many medical systems strongly influences people's health-seeking behaviour, even when Western medicines are available. Good examples include the continued use of Chinese, South Asian (Ayurvedic and Unani), Thai, Tibetan and Vietnamese medical systems as well as diverse healing practices in Africa (also true in Ethiopia) and Latin America. The continued importance of traditional medicine to the estimated 1.24 billion people in China is a well-known example, with herbal preparations accounting for 30–50 percent of total medicinal consumption in China (WHO, 2003).

Traditional medicine takes a holistic approach where disease or misfortune results from an imbalance between the individual and the social environment, whereas modern biomedicine takes a technical and analytical approach. This is also the reason behind the often-uneasy relationship between traditional and modern medicine. Both rural and urban patients commonly consult traditional healers before, after or simultaneously with consultation with medical doctors, often switching between different medical systems according to the ailment (Hassan, 2007; Cunningham *et al.*, 2008).

2.2.4 Risks associated with medicinal plants

Herbal medicines have natural origins, but natural does not mean non-toxic. Like pharmaceutical drugs, herbal medicines need to be harvested, stored, prepared and prescribed with attention to

safety, quality and efficacy. In rural areas where healthy stocks of favoured species remain, healers are able to harvest quality products locally. Safety, quality and efficacy are more difficult to achieve in urban areas, or where rural healers have to buy favoured species from traders. In Nigeria, for example, all herbal medicines tested contained heavy metals (Obi *et al.*, 2006, cited in Cunningham *et al.*, 2008).

A similar problem was found with Asian herbal medicines, which contained arsenic, lead and mercury at levels ranging from toxic (49 per cent) to levels higher than public health guidelines (74 per cent) Garvey *et al.*, (2001). High price and scarcity due to rarity or over-harvest pose additional problems since substitution with similar-looking species with different properties becomes common. In their literature review, Yang *et al.*(2006) had identified 32 pharmaceutical drugs that interacted with herbal medicines, primarily anti-coagulants, sedatives and antidepressants, oral contraceptives, anti-HIV agents, cardiovascular drugs, immunosuppressants and anticancer drugs. Preventing these adverse reactions is important. Until South Africa's recent policy changes on supplying antiretrovirals to HIV-positive people, the use of herbal medicines such as *Hypoxis* and *Sutherlandia* were being promoted. The study carried out by Mills *et al.*, (2005) showed that the use of these African herbal medicines might put patients at risk for drug toxicity, treatment failure or viral resistance.

Adverse reactions are not restricted to herbal medicines; they also occur with pharmaceuticals. Strategies to avoid adverse reactions to herbal medicines can be developed, just as they can for pharmaceuticals. This includes understanding not only which pharmaceuticals interact with which herbal medicines, but also what drives demand for traditional medicines (Cunningham *et al.*, 2008).

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1 Study Area

Batagarawa metropolis is located within Batagarawa Local Government Area in northern Nigeria and is the capital of Katsina State. Katsina is located some 260 kilometres east of the city of Sokoto and 135 kilometres northwest of Kano, close to the border with Niger. The city is the centre of an agricultural region producing groundnuts, cotton, hides, millet and guinea corn and also has mills for producing peanut oil and steel. The city is largely Muslim, and the population of the city is mainly from the Fulani and Hausa ethnic groups.

Katsina state is located in the North-western zone of Nigeria with 34 Local Government Areas (Katsina town is the state capital and largest settlement) and has a total area of 24,192 km² (Tukur *et al.*, 2013). The state is linked to the rest parts of the country and the neighbouring Niger Republic by several road networks including the two highways linking the state and Nigeria with Maradi and Zinder in Niger Republic.

The state spans between longitude 10°33'59" to 13°18'30"N and latitude 6°59'32" to 9°00'0.1"E with a total population of 5,792,578 people according to the 2006 population census. It is mainly inhabited by Hausa and Fulani people and by a few Maguzawas. Farming is the main occupation; peanuts (groundnuts) are the main cash crops. Millet and sorghum are grown as staple foods, and there is vegetable gardening in riverine floodplains. Most of its people own cattle, sheep, or goats, and hides and skins are sold for profit.

The climate of Katsina state is a tropical wet and dry type (tropical continental climate). Annual rainfall normally falls between May and September yearly, with a peak in August. The average

annual rainfall is about 700mm. The pattern of rainfall in the area is highly variable; and so result in severe and widespread droughts that can impose serious social-economic constraints (Abajeet *al.*, 2012). The mean annual temperature ranges from 29°C – 31°C. The highest air temperature normally occurs in April/May and the lowest in December through February. Evapotranspiration is generally high throughout the year. The highest amount of evaporation occurs during the dry season. The dominant vegetation of the area is the Sudan savannah type which combines the characteristics and species of both the Guinea and Sahel Savannah (Abajeet *al.*, 2012; Tukur *et al.*, 2013).

3.2 Reconnaissance Survey

Before the start of the actual research work for this study, a reconnaissance survey was carried out in order to gain a general understanding of the characteristics of the study areas and to identify the different sites in the different plant community types. It made bases for the selection of specific research sites and data collection techniques.

3.3 Data Collection

Ethnobotanical data were obtained using questionnaires and interviews. The questions were based on the objectives of the research and are written in the English language. However, for those who cannot read or understand the language, a research assistant was employed who took the pain of ensuring proper completion of the Questionnaire. The target group for the studies are herbalists, traditional medical practitioners, traditional midwives, traditional birth attendants, civil servants, farmers and other people mostly of old age who have practised and used medicinal plants.

In order to ascertain the validity of the instrument that was used in this research, the questionnaires were drafted and the copies were given to the supervisor of this research for validation and vetting.

On the basis of their suggestions and recommendations, a correction was made in the drafted copies.

3.4 Plants Collection

A Field survey was conducted to collect the plants. A typical specimen of a vascular plant was collected for each plant. The plant comprises of the flora and vegetative parts. The samples were pressed immediately. Identification of the plant was conducted in the herbarium of the Biological Department of Umaru Musa Yar'adua University Katsina.

3.5 Data Analysis and Interpretation of the Result

The Data generated from the study were tabulated in Microsoft Excel sheets and uploaded to the statistical package for social sciences (SPSS version 21). The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Chi-square (χ^2) analysis was used to compare the differences while plants species popularity was analyzed using ethnobotanical tools such as Relative Frequency of Citation (RFC). The result was presented using tables, charts and pictures. $RFC = F_c / N$ where F_c is the number of respondents who cited a particular species and N is the total number of the respondents.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS

4.1 Socio – demographic information of the respondents

The demographic characteristics of the respondents were determined and recorded through face-to-face interviews. A total of 93 respondents were included in this survey. Most respondents (34.41%, n = 32) were between the ages of 46–60 years, followed by those between the age of 61-75 years (25.81%, n = 24), respondents within the age range of 31-45 years had accounted for 18.28% (n=17) of the responses while those that belong within the range of 16-30 years had accounted for 11.83 (n =11) of the response (Table 4.1). Similarly, the majority of the respondents (29.03%, n = 27) are healers, and 27.96% (n = 26) of the respondents are medicinal herb users while 12 among them (12.90%) are rural doctors and 18.28% (n = 17) are medicinal herb dealers (Table 4.1).

4.2 Medicinal Importance of the Identified Plants

A total of forty medicinal plants species belonging to twenty-one families as having medicinal properties against different human ailments used by the local community were collected and recorded in this study. The medicinal plant resource in the area is considerable. Leaves were also found to be the most harvested plant parts for the preparation of the remedies (42.5%) followed by stem (27.5%) and roots (17.5%). In the preparation of medicines, single plants were used to prepare the medicines to cure the diseases rather than mixing with each other.

None of the respondents mentioned any side effects caused by any of the medicinal plants listed in Table 4.2. All in all, these plants are used for the treatment of 26 types of ailments. Most of the traditional healers obtain their extracts by boiling (decoction) the medicinal plants). Their

methods of administering treatments vary from drying and burning the plants for treating warts with the smoke, to applying the remedy topically for haemorrhoids.

The traditional healers usually collect the plants in the field, dry and crush them, before storing the plant material in bottles; this is often done to prevent patients from recognizing the plants being used for their treatment, which may sometimes be a seemingly ordinary plant growing in their gardens or across the street or in the field. Some healers prefer storing plant material in powdered form in bottles to reduce the number of field collection trips they may otherwise be obliged to undertake or to store up inventory for times when some plants may be seasonably unavailable, so as to be able to offer treatments throughout the year.

4.3 Diversity and Abundance of the Plants

All plant species identified by this study have local vernacular names. A total of sixty-five (65) plant species belonging to 32 families were documented from the study area, Fabaceae (46.88%, $n = 15$) has the highest number of appearances followed by Moraceae, and Combretaceae (15.63 $n = 5$, each) (Table 4.2).

The identified plant density, relative density, frequency and relative density is presented in Table 4.3. The Species richness, evenness and Shannon-Weiner diversity indices of the plant were presented in Table 4.5 The highest species richness and maximum diversity was observed in site E, while site D was with the least species richness and diversity. The evenness was more or less similar for each community except that the maximum evenness was observed in site B and in site D.

Species numbers are thus not directly comparable due to the lack of standardization of sampling effort (e.g number of questionnaires, number and length transect walks and search time) and reference area. In order to derive comparable estimates for medicinal plant species richness and

prevalence in time and space, a common methodology needs to be applied (Gotelli and Colwell, 2001; Whittaker *et al.*, 2001).

4.4. Mode of Preparation and Route of Administration of the Identified Medicinal Plants

Recipes were made from a combination of different parts and/or different plant species, while some were made from single plant parts. Maceration is the main method of preparation of the medicinal plant (45%, n = 18) followed by Decoction (40%, n = 18), other methods include: steaming and smoking. Similarly, the routes of administration are mainly internal in which oral administration is the common one (77.5%), other routes of administration include: topical and inhaling.

Table 4.1: Socio – demographic information of the respondents

Variable	Specification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Age	16-30	11.00	11.83
	31-45	17.00	18.28
	46-60	32.00	34.41
	61-75	24.00	25.81
	>75	9.00	9.68
	Total		93.00
Practice	Healer	27.00	29.03
	Medicinal Herb dealer	17.00	18.28
	Medicinal Herb user	26.00	27.96
	Rural Doctors	12.00	12.90
	Others	11.00	11.83
	Total		93.00

Table 4.2: Vascular Plants Identified in the Study Area

S/N	Botanical Name	Hausa Name	Family
1	<i>Acacia nolitica</i>	Bagaruwa	Fabaceae
2	<i>Acacia aneura</i>	Malga	Fabaceae
3	<i>Acacia senegal</i>	Dakwara	Fabaceae
4	<i>Acacia sieberana</i>	Farar Kaya	Fabaceae
5	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Kuka	Bombaceae
6	<i>Albizia chevalieri</i>	Katsari	Fabaceae
7	<i>Anarcadium occidentale</i>	Yazawa	Anarcadiaceae
8	<i>Annisopusmannii</i>	Sakayau	Apocynaceae
9	<i>Annona senegalensis</i>	GwandanDaji	Annonaceae
10	<i>Anogeissusleiocarpus</i>	Marke	Combretaceae
11	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Dalbejiya	Meliaceae
12	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	Aduwa	Zygophyllaceae
13	<i>Bauhaniarufescens</i>	Tsatstsagi	Fabaceae
14	<i>Bauhinia thonningii</i>	Kalgo	Fabaceae
15	<i>Borassus aethiopum</i>	Giginya	Arecaceae
16	<i>Calatropsisprocera</i>	Tumpapiya	Apocynaceae
17	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	Rimi	Malvaceae
18	<i>Citrus limon</i>	LemunTsami	Rutaceae
19	<i>Combretum collinum</i>	Tarmniya	Combretaceae
20	<i>Combretum micranthum</i>	Geza	Combretaceae
21	<i>Commiphoraaficana</i>	Dashi	Burseraceae
22	<i>Daniella oliveri</i>	Maaje	Fabaceae
23	<i>Detariummicrocapum</i>	Taura	Fabaceae
24	<i>Dichrostatachyscinera</i>	Sarkakiya	Fabaceae
25	<i>Diospyrusespiliforms</i>	Kanya	Ebnaceae
26	<i>Erythrina senegalensis</i>	Minjirya	Papilionaceae
27	<i>Eucalyptus camadulensis</i>	Turare	Myrthceae
28	<i>Euphorbia balsamifera</i>	Aliyara	Euphorbiaceae
29	<i>Faidherbia albida</i>	Gawo	Fabaceae
30	<i>Ficus platyphylla</i>	Gamji	Moraceae
31	<i>Ficus iteophylla</i>	Shiriya	Moraceae
32	<i>Ficus polita</i>	Durumi	Moraceae
33	<i>Ficus sycomorous</i>	Baure	Moraceae
34	<i>Ficus thonningii</i>	Chediya	Moraceae
35	<i>Gomphrena celesioides</i>	NononKurciya	Amaranthaceae
36	<i>Guierasenegalesis</i>	Barbarta	Combretaceae
37	<i>Gymnosporiasenegalesis</i>	NamijinTsada	Celastraceae
38	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i>	Yakuwa	Malvaceae

39	<i>Hyphaenathebaica</i>	Goruba	Arecaceae
40	<i>Jatropha curcas</i>	Chindazugu	Euphorbiaceae
41	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	Madachi	Meliaceae
42	<i>Kigelia Africana</i>	Rawaya	Bignoniaceae
43	<i>Lawsoniainermis</i>	Lalle	Lythraceae
44	<i>Lenneamicrocarpa</i>	Faru	Anacardiaceae
45	<i>Leptadeniahastata</i>	Yadiya	Asclepiadaceae
46	<i>Magnifera indica L.</i>	Mangwaro	Anacardiaceae
47	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Zogale	Moringaceae
48	<i>Oleo europea</i>	Zaitun	Oleaceae
49	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Dorowa	Fabaceae
50	<i>Prosopis africana</i>	Kiryia	Mimaceae
51	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Gwaba	Myrtaceae
52	<i>Punica granatum</i>	Ruman	Lythraceae
53	<i>Sclerocarya</i>	Danya	Anacardiaceae
54	<i>Securidacal longipedunculata</i>	Sanya	Polygaceae
55	<i>Senna occidentalis</i>	TafasarMasar	Fabaceae
56	<i>Strychnos spinosa</i>	Kokiya	Loganiaceae
57	<i>Syzygiumguineense</i>	Malmo	Myrtaceae
58	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	Tsamiya	Fabaceae
59	<i>Terminalliacattapa</i>	Umbrella	Combretaceae
60	<i>Uvariachamae</i>	Rukuki	Annonaceae
61	<i>Veroniaglaberrina</i>	Shuwaka	Compositae
62	<i>Vitex doniana</i>	Dinya	Lamiaceae
63	<i>Vitilleriaparadoxa</i>	Kadanya	Sapotaceae
64	<i>Ziziphus spina-christi</i>	Kurna	Fabaceae
65	<i>Zizypusmaritania</i>	Magarya	Rhamnaceae

Table 4.3: Density, Relative Density, Frequency and Relative Density of the Identified Plants

S/N	Plants	Density	Frequency	Relative Density	Relative frequency
1	<i>Acacia anuera</i>	0.56	40	3.98	1.59
2	<i>Acacia nilotica</i>	0.2	40	1.42	1.59
3	<i>Acacia senegal</i>	0.16	40	1.14	1.59
4	<i>Acacia sieberana</i>	0.04	20	0.28	0.79
5	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	0.16	20	1.14	0.79
6	<i>Albizia chavaleri</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
7	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
8	<i>Annisopusmannii</i>	0.12	40	0.85	1.59
9	<i>Annona senegalensis</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
10	<i>Anogeissusleiocarpus</i>	0.32	40	2.27	1.59
11	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	2.16	100	15.34	3.97
12	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	0.04	20	0.28	0.79
13	<i>Bauhinia rufescens</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
14	<i>Borassus aetheopum</i>	0.04	20	0.28	0.79
15	<i>Calatropsisprocera</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
16	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	0.16	40	1.14	1.59
17	<i>Citrus limon</i>	0.12	40	0.85	1.59
18	<i>Combretum collinum</i>	0.16	60	1.14	2.38
19	<i>Combretum micranthum</i>	0.12	20	0.85	0.79
20	<i>Commiphoraafricana</i>	0.04	20	0.28	0.79
21	<i>Daniella oliveri</i>	0.12	40	0.85	1.59
22	<i>Detariummicrocarpum</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
23	<i>Dichrostatachyscinera</i>	0.16	20	1.14	0.79
24	<i>Diospyrusmespiliforms</i>	0.56	40	3.98	1.59
25	<i>Erythrina senegalensis</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
26	<i>Eucalyptus camadulensis</i>	0.52	40	3.69	1.59
27	<i>Euphorbia balsamifera</i>	0.24	40	1.7	1.59
28	<i>Faidherbia albida</i>	0.28	40	1.99	1.59
29	<i>Ficus iteophylla</i>	0.04	20	0.28	0.79
30	<i>Ficus platyphylla</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
31	<i>Ficus polita</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
32	<i>Ficus sycomorous</i>	0.24	40	1.7	1.59
33	<i>Ficus thonningii</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
34	<i>Gomphrena celesioides</i>	0.12	20	0.85	0.79
35	<i>Gueira senegalensis</i>	0.24	60	1.7	2.38

36	<i>Gymnosporia senegalensis</i>	0.08	40	0.57	1.59
37	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
38	<i>Hyphaenathebaica</i>	0.16	60	1.14	2.38
39	<i>Jatropha curcas</i>	0.4	60	2.84	2.38
40	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	0.24	60	1.7	2.38
41	<i>Kigeliaafricana</i>	0.04	20	0.28	0.79
42	<i>Lawsoniainermis</i>	0.16	40	1.14	1.59
43	<i>Lenneamicrocarpa</i>	0.2	40	1.42	1.59
44	<i>Leptadaniahastata</i>	0.52	60	3.69	2.38
45	<i>Magnifera indica L.</i>	0.36	60	2.56	2.38
46	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	0.48	80	3.41	3.17
47	<i>Oleo europhia</i>	0.12	40	0.85	1.59
48	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	0.28	60	1.99	2.38
49	<i>Piliostigmareticulatum</i>	0.4	60	2.84	2.38
50	<i>Prosopis africana</i>	0.08	40	0.57	1.59
51	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	0.04	20	0.28	0.79
52	<i>Punica granatum</i>	0.12	20	0.85	0.79
53	<i>Sclerocaryabirrea</i>	0.24	20	1.7	0.79
54	<i>Securidacalongipedunculata</i>	0.16	40	1.14	1.59
55	<i>Senna occidentalis</i>	0.24	20	1.7	0.79
56	<i>Strychnos spinosa</i>	0.12	40	0.85	1.59
57	<i>Syzygiumguineense</i>	0.12	40	0.85	1.59
58	<i>Tamarindus indica</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
59	<i>Terminalliacattapa</i>	0.04	20	0.28	0.79
60	<i>Uvariachamae</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
61	<i>Veroniaglabberina</i>	0.08	20	0.57	0.79
62	<i>Vitex doniana</i>	0.2	80	1.42	3.17
63	<i>Vitilleriaparadoxa</i>	0.12	40	0.85	1.59
64	<i>Ziziphus spina-christi</i>	0.16	40	1.14	1.59
65	<i>Zizypusmaritania</i>	0.12	20	0.85	0.79

Table 4.4: Medicinal Importance of Some Common Plants

S/N	Botanical name	Local name	Part used	Cure
1	<i>Acacia nolitica</i>	Bagaruwa	Leaves	Diarrhea and neonatal disorders
2	<i>Acacia senegal</i>	Dakwara	Stem	Stomach disturbance
3	<i>Acacia sieberana</i>	Farar Kaya	Leaves	Malaria, jaundice
4	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Kuka	Stem	Malaria and Diarrhea
5	<i>Anarcadium occidentale</i>	Yazawa	Leaves and fruits	Malaria and Cholera
6	<i>Annona senegalensis</i>	GwandanDaji	Stem	Dysentery
7	<i>Anogeissusleiocarpus</i>	Marke	Root	Dysentery
8	<i>Azadichrata indica</i>	Darbejia	Leaves	Measles and Diarrhea
9	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	Aduwa	Stem	Anemia
10	<i>Bauhinia thonningii</i>	Kalgo	Root	Arthritis, wound
11	<i>Calatropsisprocera</i>	Tumpapiya	Stem	Catarrh, Cough
12	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	Rimi	Leaves	Anti-anemia
13	<i>Citrus limon</i>	LemunTsami	Leaves and fruits	Pile and Malaria
14	<i>Detariummicrocapum</i>	Taura	Root	Diarrhea, dysentery
15	<i>Diospyrusmespiliformis</i>	Kanya	Leaves	Malaria and Cholera
16	<i>Eucalyptus camadulensis</i>	Turare	Leaves	Malaria
17	<i>Euphorbia balsamifera</i>	Aliyara	Root	Typhoid, malaria
18	<i>Ficus platyphylum</i>	Gamji	Stem	Respiratory tract infections
19	<i>Ficus polita</i>	Durumi	Leaves and fruits	Malaria, dysentery, gonorrhoea, rheumatism
20	<i>Ficus sycomorous</i>	Baure	Root	Stomach pain, Deworming
21	<i>Ficus thonningii</i>	Chediya	Leaves	Malaria and Typhoid
22	<i>Guierasenegalesis</i>	Barbarta	Leaves	Dysentery, diarrhoea
23	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i>	Yakuwa	Stem	Gastroenteritis and Asthma
24	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	Madaci	Stem	Pile
25	<i>Kigelia Africana</i>	Rawaya	Stem	Diarrhea
26	<i>Lawsoniainermis</i>	Lalle	Leaves	Chicken Fox
27	<i>Lennea macrocarpa</i>	Faru	Stem	Eczema and common cold
28	<i>Leptadeniahastata</i>	Yadiya	Leaves	Gastroenteritis
29	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Mangwaro	Leaves	Malaria
30	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Zogala	Leaves	Malaria, Ulcer and Gastroenteritis
31	<i>Oleo europea</i>	Zaitun	Leaves and fruits	Malaria, diabetes and to improve women fertility

32	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Dorowa	Root	Diabetics, venereal disease, gonorrhoea, watery sperm
33	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Gwaba	Stem and Leaves	Cholera, Typhoid and Asthma
34	<i>Punica granatum</i>	Ruman	Leaves	Gastroenteritis and Asthma
35	<i>Terminalliacattapa</i>	Umbrella	Leaves	Eczema and common cold
36	<i>Veroniaglaberrina</i>	Shuwaka	Stem	Diarrhea and Cholera
37	<i>Vitex doniana</i>	Dinya	Leaves	Ear infection and Conjunctivitis
38	<i>Vitilleriaparadoxa</i>	Kadanya	Leaves	Respiratory tract infections
39	<i>Ziziphus spina-christi</i>	Kurna	Leaves	Dysentery, diarrhoea
40	<i>Zizypusmaritania</i>	Magarya	Root	Gastroenteritis

Figure 4.1: Parts of the Plant Used in the treatment of diseases

4.5. Mode of Preparation and Route of Administration of the Identified Medicinal Plants

S/N	Botanical name	Local name	Method of Preparation	Mode of Administration
1	<i>Acacia nolitica</i>	Bagaruwa	Decoction	Topical/Oral
2	<i>Acacia senegal</i>	Dakwara	Decoction	Oral
3	<i>Acacia sieberana</i>	Farar Kaya	Decoction	Topical
4	<i>Adansonia digitata</i>	Kuka	Decoction	Oral
5	<i>Anarcadium occidentale</i>	Yazawa	Steaming	Oral
6	<i>Annona senegalensis</i>	GwandanDaji	Smoking	Inhaling
7	<i>Anogeissusleiocarpus</i>	Marke	Decoction	Oral
8	<i>Azadichrata indica</i>	Darbejia	Decoction	Oral
9	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i>	Aduwa	Smoking	Inhaling
10	<i>Bauhinia thonningii</i>	Kalgo	Maceration	Oral
11	<i>Calatropsisprocera</i>	Tumpapiya	Maceration/steaming	Topical/Oral
12	<i>Ceiba pentandra</i>	Rimi	Maceration	Oral
13	<i>Citrus limon</i>	LemunTsami	Maceration	Oral
14	<i>Detariummicrocapum</i>	Taura	Decoction	Oral
15	<i>Diospyrusmespiliformis</i>	Kanya	Maceration	Topical
16	<i>Eucalyptus camadulensis</i>	Turare	Maceration	Oral
17	<i>Euphorbia balsamifera</i>	Aliyara	Maceration	Oral
18	<i>Ficus platyphylum</i>	Gamji	Maceration	Topical
19	<i>Ficus polita</i>	Durumi	Decoction	Oral
20	<i>Ficus sycomorous</i>	Baure	Maceration	Oral
21	<i>Ficus thonningii</i>	Chediya	Maceration	Oral
22	<i>Guierasenegalesis</i>	Barbarta	Decoction	Oral
23	<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i>	Yakuwa	Decoction	Oral
24	<i>Khaya senegalensis</i>	Madaci	Maceration	Oral
25	<i>Kigelia Africana</i>	Rawaya	Maceration	Oral
26	<i>Lawsoniainermis</i>	Lalle	Decoction or Maceration	Oral
27	<i>Lennea macrocarpa</i>	Faru	Maceration	Oral
28	<i>Leptadeniahastata</i>	Yadiya	Decoction	Oral
29	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	Mangwaro	Maceration	Oral
30	<i>Moringa oleifera</i>	Zogala	Smoking	Inhaling
31	<i>Oleo europea</i>	Zaitun	Decoction	Oral
32	<i>Parkia biglobosa</i>	Dorowa	Maceration	Oral
33	<i>Psidium guajava</i>	Gwaba	Maceration	Oral
34	<i>Punica granatum</i>	Ruman	Decoction	Oral
35	<i>Terminalliacattapa</i>	Umbrella	Maceration	Oral
36	<i>Veroniaglaberrina</i>	Shuwaka	Decoction	Oral

37	<i>Vitex doniana</i>	Dinya	Decoction	Oral
38	<i>Vitilleriaparadoxa</i>	Kadanya	Decoction	Oral
39	<i>Ziziphus spina-christi</i>	Kurna	Maceration	Topical/Oral
40	<i>Zizypusmaritania</i>	Magarya	Maceration	Oral

Figure 4.2: Mode of Preparation of the Identified Medicinal Plants

Figure 4.3: Route of Administration of the Identified Medicinal Plants

Table 4.6: Species richness, evenness and Shannon-Weiner diversity index of Plant Community

SITE	SHANNON-WEINER DIVERSITY INDEX	SIMPSON INDEX	EVENESS	MARGALEF INDEX
Site A	2.69	11.68	1.06	3.41
Site B	2.85	11.35	1.12	4.06
Site C	2.72	8.68	1.08	4.21
Site D	2.61	8.45	1.02	3.43
Site E	2.94	13.56	1.09	4.35

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Discussion

It is generally agreed that ethnobotanical survey is one of the primary steps in the identification, selection and development of drugs from medicinal plants (Newman, 2003; Yetein, 2013). Thus, the main focus of this study was to document the diversity and distribution of vascular plants in Batagarawa local government area, Katsina state – Nigeria, and their medicinal importance. Previous ethnobotanical studies were conducted in Katsina included the ethnobotanical survey of indigenous plants used in the treatment of malaria in Dutsin-ma metropolitan area of Katsina State (Liadi, 2016). Other States included Ethnopharmacological survey of medicinal plants used for the management of pediatric ailments in Kano State, Nigeria (Abubakar, 2007), Ethnobotanical Survey of Medicinal Plants in Metropolitan Kano, Nigeria (Salisu, 2015), ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants used for the treatment of malaria and ethnobotanical survey of medicinal plants used in the management of diabetes mellitus in Kano metropolis (Helen, 2017).

A total of sixty-five (65) plant species belonging to 32 families were documented from the study area. The species richness of medicinal plants appears to be rather low compared to those in other studies in Eastern Africa (Gidayet *al.*, 2003; Nanyingiet *al.*, 2008). In former studies with similar methodology 56 medicinal plant species are recorded for the Kankia LGA within Katsina State with an area of 21,000 km² (Nanyingiet *al.*, 2008) and (Fratkin, 1996) named about 120 plant species. A recent ethnobotanical survey recorded 25 species (Omwengaet *al.*, 2015). For Ethiopia, 33 species are found in an area of 434 km² (Gidayet *al.*, 2003).

The Fabaceae, Moraceae, and Combretaceae families provided the highest proportion of plant species collected in this study. Previous studies also indicated that the families Fabaceae, Poaceae and Combretaceae have many species used in the management of different diseases in Northern Nigeria (Maliwichi-Nyirenda, 2010; Rahman, 2014; Kavya, 2013).

The ethnomedicinal uses of some of the plant species identified in this study were also reported in previous ethnobotanical studies conducted in Kano State. These species include *A. sativum*, *B. dalzielii*, *C. papaya*, *C. singueana*, *F. thoningii*, *G. senegalensis*, *M. hirtus* and *P. biglobosa* (Sani, 2011; Salisu, 2010).

Azadirachta indica was the most frequently mentioned plant species. Previous studies indicated that *Azadirachta indica* was used in African traditional medicine for the management of various ailments, some of which have also been reported in this study (Sani, 2011). Many pharmacological activities have been reported for this important plant which includes; antimicrobial, anthelmintic, antiplasmodial, trypanocidal, leishmanicidal, antioxidant and hepatoprotective activities (Salisu, 2005; Gedson, 2012; Ahmad, 2014; Tiwo, 1999; Kubmarawa, 2007; Adigun, 2007; Soro, 2013; Vonthron-Senecheau, 2003; Akanbi, 2012; Victor, 2013). Therefore, *Azadirachta indica* could be considered as a promising candidate for further scientific evaluations in the search for new, effective and affordable drugs.

Regarding the present study, it was observed that different parts of plants were reported to be used for the herbal preparations, with leaves and stem bark being the most frequently used parts. This finding is in agreement with other researches (Abubakar, 2017; Olutayo, 2011; Atawodi, 2011). The use of leaves could be due to the abundance of phytochemical constituents (Sonibare, 2009). Leaves are considered as the main synthesis site of phytochemical constituents and are the most commonly used plant parts by traditional medicine practitioners (Atawodi, 2011).

5.2 Conclusion

The present study has provided a data bank for some medicinal plants that are used in the treatment of ailments within Batagarawa LGA, Katsina State. This study has also provided additional information on the relevance of Plants in the treatment of various diseases within Batagarawa LGA, it is a step forward towards investigating the medicinal plants diversity in Nigerian flora. The study also revealed that there was high diversity of medicinal Plants and traditional knowledge about the use, preparation and applications of these medicinal plants in Batagarawa LGA.

The number of medicinal plants and their potential applications in humans reflect the rich ethnomedicinal knowledge in Batagarawa communal area. The preservation of this knowledge is due to continued reliance on wild plant resources for primary healthcare by the local community. Wide use of herbal medicine by both young children and adults will result in passing on of this indigenous knowledge to future generations. A strong belief in the effectiveness of traditional medicine in the primary healthcare of Batagarawa community will contribute to the persistence of this knowledge in the local community. The pharmaceutical importance of medicinal plants in Batagarawa communal area and documented indigenous practices can contribute much to national drug development if it receives the attention it deserves. While traditional healers claimed a high level of efficacy from their herbal remedies, it is important to standardize the drug preparation, dilution, dosage and route of administration, so as to match western medicine procedures. The study results suggest that there is a need for validation of the reported species for their efficacy.

Since leaves were the most widely used plant parts and plants were mostly collected from the plants, the risk of plant resources loss is high in Batagarawa communal area. Awareness

programme should be made to the traditional leaders, traditional healers and the community at large to safeguard such a rich heritage of indigenous knowledge and medicinal plant use. This will assist in the sustainable utilization and conservation of the plant resources in the study area. Sustainable management of the herbal medicines must be balanced with the short-term needs of the people for their basic healthcare needs and protection of the natural resource base. Protection of the herbal medicines should be viewed as a longer-term goal for ensuring that the resource base is utilized wisely so that it can continue to provide benefits to the local community on a sustainable basis.

5.3 Recommendations

1. Government, non-governmental organizations, institutions and other development partners should enlighten traditional medicinal practitioners in exploring the knowledge in order to avoid loss of trend of the knowledge hence its restricted to a particular family.
2. Researches on the effectiveness of other plants should be done.
3. Toxicity studies of the effective plants should be done to determine the safety indices of the plants.

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